

Research Article

The Seven Pillars of Christian Counseling: Bedrock to Christian Education

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Abstract

The counseling process seeks to provide a fountain of resources for the needy believer who finds his or her self-enmeshed in some inevitable changes associated with growing up in life generally. Since the spiritual life is a pivot in which other department of life revolves, the average believer over times seeks succor and in the warm interaction with an older more experienced believer who had been more acquainted with the road map of the kingdom of God. Of work, the Christian counselor may not be a guru but his training and inherence exposure by the vicissitudes of life equipped him or her with functional knowledge and experience coupled with the enablement of the Holy Spirit, the Christian counselor furnishes the needy believer with an avalanche of remedies that presents a ready balm to many a social or emotional as well as spiritual malaise. Dispensed in an enabling environment, these interactions that take place between a counselor and counselee provides a firm launching pad for the growth of the individual believer and the church universally ability to face new challenges and to tap the sources of renewal is one of the secrets of Christianity's growth. The way forward usually meant a studied look back ward, back to the image of God revealed in the story of Jesus. Christians have always considered the age of Jesus and his apostles a kind of model for all the other ages. It gave to the church its faith in Jesus, the resurrected Messiah, and the hope of forgiveness of sins through him. And the Age demonstrated in the life of Paul, that the gospel of grace recognizes no boundaries of nation, race, sex, or culture.

Keywords: *seven pillars, Christian counseling bedrock and Christian education*

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Introduction

Christian counselling originated from God after the creation of man in the Garden of Eden. It is an integral part of the Christian theological educational system. Christian counselling programmes for Christians, theological and Christian education are designed to address the spiritual, physical, emotional and social difficulties of individual or group members of Christendom or theological students. This is to compliment skilful spiritual/preaching and theological learning in the class room and also enhance the spiritual and academic performance or achievements of the church members or Bible School Students and independent churches as well.

Christian counselling plays vital role on preventing Christians and Bible School Students from personal, social, mental, emotional, material and other similar problems among Christians, church members, General Over-seers, church leaders and the world at large.

The Concept of Counseling Process:

Counseling has defiled a single meaning or a single definition. In order to understand and grasp the full meaning of counseling, it might be helpful to consider what counseling is not. First of all, counseling is not just an event or an exercise or something that happens between two people. Counseling is not an advice-giving process. Commenting on advice-giving as different from counseling, Guardini (1993) notes that: the knowledge and life experience of the adviser are the chief sources of advice. This advice springs from the practical reason of the adviser, solicited by the other person. Advice is the opinion of an expert about a particular case. Advice usually concerns a particular behavioral problem. It does not reach to the core of the person.

To give advice means to impart answers and give solutions to the person who asked for them (P.17).

Counseling therefore, is not the same as advice-giving. Advice-giving normally entails telling people what they should do or ought to do or should not do. Such thing is not allowed in counseling.

During a counseling encounter, the counselor helps the client/counselee to look at the available possibilities or opportunities and gain control. The counselor will not tell the client what he or she should do. This is helping the client assume or take responsibility on what he or she does. For instance, a client may ask the counselor "what would you

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advise me to do in this situation? The counselor could rightly respond by saying, **“let us explore the ideas you have” or what ideas do you have?** Such response helps the clients to realize that he or she should play some part in arriving at the right answer. Counseling, therefore as different from advice-giving, empowers the client to take full control after exploring all available options. The above definition of counseling from what it is not leaves room for more understanding of what counseling means. **Counseling is a helping relationship that exists between a counselor (a professional) and a client.** Several authors have provided the definition of counseling along the lines of helping relationship. Hayes and Hopson (1981, Pg. 276) define counseling as “helping people explore problems so that they can decide what to do about them”. What is implied is that counseling and helping are indeed synonymous. The general aim of helping is to assist someone to take more control of his or her own life.

Some other definitions of counseling are available within the relevant literature. The British Association of Counseling (BAC, 1984) believes that the term “counseling” includes work with individuals and with relationships which may develop into crisis support, psychotherapeutic, guiding or problem solving Burks and Sterfflre (1979 P.14) believe that “counseling denotes a professional relationship between a trained counselor and a client. This relationship is usually person to person, although it may sometimes involve more than two people. **It is designed to help the clients to understand and clarify their views of their life-space and to learn their self-determined goals through meaningful, well-informed choices and through resolution of an emotional or interpersonal nature”.** Fehtma and Dryden provide a more in-depth definition of counseling as quoted in Mcleod (1998) **as: a principle relationship characterized by the application of one or more psychological theories and recognized set of communication skills, modified by experience, intuition and other interpersonal factors, to client’s intimate concerns, problems or aspirations.**

Its predominant ethos is one of facilitation rather than of advice-giving or coercion. It may be very brief or long duration, takes place in an organizational or private practice setting and may or may not overlap with practical, medical and matters of personal welfare. It is both a distinctive activity undertaken by people agreeing to occupy the roles of a counselor and a client and it is an emerging profession. It is a service sought by people in distress or in some degree of confusion who wish to discuss and resolve these in a relationship which is more disciplined and confidential than friendship (P.3).

It is easy to deduce from the above definitions that counseling can have different meanings. In those definitions, the ideas of helping, relationship and communication have been raised. Such contrasting interpretations may not be unconnected with the process by which counseling has metamorphosed in modern times.

What are the seven pillars of Christian counseling as a bed rock of Christian Education?

The Seven Pillars of Counseling

Introduction:

Romans Chapter 5:14 presents the duty and rules of true counseling, Paul writing: I myself also am persuaded of you, my brethren, that ye also are full of goodness, filled with all knowledge, able also to admonish one another. The Greek word for admonish means to place in the mind, it may be an exhortation or a warning in the form of a warm, friendly urging to honor some duty or objectives. We often connect admonition with words of reproof, but the Greek term has a broader use than that, what is placed in the mind may certainly be a caution or reproof, but it may equally be the gentlest suggestion or encouragement.

Three other verses on the place of admonition should also influence us, the first being Colossians 3:16 "Let the word of Christ dwell in you richly in all wisdom, teaching and admonishing one another in Psalms and hymns spiritual songs singing with grace in your hearts to the Lord".

Noted exegetes say that the semi-colon in this verse rightly belongs after the words one another, for we admonish by word, so, for example, if we see some friend who is not attending meetings regularly, or if we see another sliding into covetousness, then prayerfully we get alongside to bring the standards of the word for we all have a part in the ministry of admonishing one another.

Looking also at the letter to the Hebrews, Chapter 3, and verse 12 - 13, here the duty of believers to help each other check any decline, we are to intervene and assist wherever necessary and whenever possible, of course, we have to cultivate the right spirit and we will touch on that in a moment but, first we read from Hebrews 10:23-24.

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'Let us hold fast the profession of our faith without wavering, (for he is faithful that promised) and let us consider one another to provoke unto love and to good works'. The admonition term is not used here (or in the other Hebrews verse) but it is the same thought. We have a duty of mutual ministering, returning to Romans 15:14, we are given some of the qualifications for this ministry, Paul saying that the people were full of goodness and filled with all knowledge.

Goodness (meaning the qualities of kindness and consideration) is essential if we are to counsel others. Equally it is vital to be filled with all knowledge which refers to knowledge of the Bible, not of human wisdom.

Make no mistake; however, this is a dangerous ministry, with the potential, if mishandled, to destroy precious friendships and even whole fellowships. For this reason we must spend a short time taking a kind of bath and considering some of the qualifications we require and the spirit in which we should go about this ministry. Therefore our first counsel comes from the words of Christ recorded in Luke 6:37 and 41. "Judge not, and ye shall not be judged: condemn not and ye shall not be condemned: forgive and ye shall be forgiven --- And why be holiest thou the mote that is in thy brothers eye, but perceives not the beam that is in thine own eye?"

This caution highlights the disaster of a superior spirit, or a critical spirit, in helping one another abomination must be approached with humility, considering (or examining) ourselves, lest thou also be tempted (Galatians 6:1).

We all have many sins, fallings weaknesses and difficulties of which we should be deeply aware. We will ourselves fall in some respect, and need the help and even the reproof of others and we are to approach one another in that humble spirit of awareness. The humility is very apparent to the person we seek to help and makes our admonition acceptable, whereas the person who hands out advice from a dizzy height is seldom acceptable.

4. A counsel from the words of the Lord urges us to be ready to share our own spiritual lessons and experiences. Luke 6: 45 reads: "A good man out of the good treasure of his heart brings forth that which is good and an evil man that which is evil".

This verse refers to gracious deeds and uplifting, edifying conversations but when applied to the ministry of admonition, the good man naturally urges and comforts from the treasure of his experience of God's grace toward him.

Giving admonition can be a very humbling experience, if we see someone heading into a problem that we ourselves once had, we must be ready to acknowledge that we did that same foolish thing and fell into a snare. Admonition, as we have noted is not from a dizzy height, our counsel will come from the Bible and be supplemented from our own experience of failure and recovery and we must be ready for this.

5. The third counsel is from Luke 17: 1-2, there is a remarkable serious caution and while it primarily applies to children, it surely applies also to all God's spiritual children. The Lord said to his disciples, "It is impossible but that offences will come: but woe unto him, through whom they come? It was better for him that a millstone was hanged about his neck and he cast into the sea, than that he should offend one of these little ones".

The caution for the ministry of personal admonition is that there should be no callous, rough handling; we have to be very careful, fair and well-moderated in this ministry, and not go for a person, hitting this way and that. For one thing, the problem we think we see in that person may not be the true picture and we may have misread the apparent evidence. The person may be entirely innocent, or there may be factors which greatly reduce any blame. Further, the straying person may have been spoken to by others already and will feel caught in an avalanche of criticism, admonition never sets out to inflict pain dislike, irritation or vengeance and if it does, according to Christ's caution, the admonisher becomes the guilty party so we deal with one another as respected and valued fellow believers and never in a rough, cavalier kind of way.

From Luke 17:3-4, which states thus: "Take heed to yourselves: if thy brother trespass against thee, rebuke him and if he repent, forgive him. And if he trespass against thee seven times in a day, and seven times in a day turn again to thee, saying, I repent, thou shalt forgive him". The key point here is that motive matters to be qualified to engage in mutual shepherding

we must possess a sincere desire to see advance rather than to be seen as the instructor or anything of that kind, what is our motive? Is it really to help and to see the Lord glorified and his work speeded forward? Is there true sympathy in our heart? In Romans 12:15 Paul writes, Rejoice with them that do rejoice and weep with them that weep. This is the spirit of mutual personal ministry.

6. Following these counsel and personal ministry, if readers are familiar with the new genre of counseling books, chiefly drawn from secular insights, they will notice at once that these pillars are about changing people not behavior.
7. **Holiness is the Goal:** - The first and the most obvious aim of personal ministry is that of promoting holiness and character, our Romans 15:14 text contains the words-full of goodness which is a qualification for mutual admonition.

Trust Promoted:

Our second pillar of personal ministry is the building of faith, as expressed in Romans 15:13. Now the God of hope fills you with all Joy and peace in believing, that you may abound in hope, through the power of the Holy Ghost". This is a life of faith and we are to be advancing in trust in God, is someone very low, troubled or anxious? Then that believer needs to be encouraged to trust the Lord no matter what, to trust in his providential dealings, to commit his all to the Lord, and to pray for the strength to go through difficult situations. In mutual admonition we help each other not to fall into self-pity, grumbling and groaning and considering ourselves badly dealt with. We exhort to faith, for we are the Lord's and know that he will not let things happen to us, which we cannot deal with by his help through every situation of life, he train us, perhaps even chasing us, but he is at work and we must trust him. The task of bringing one another to deeper trust, laying hold on the Lord and praying and rejoicing in his love is the great aim or pillar of personal, mutual shepherding.

Reflection Deepened: third pillar of mutual personal encouragement is the promotion of sincere worship and reflection, referred to in Romans 15:6. "That ye may with one mind and one mouth glorify God even the Father of our Lord Jesus Christ." Paul goes on to speak of God's promises that the Gentiles would praise him (verses 10 and 11) we could refer again to Colossian 3:16 where the exhortation to mutual admonition flows into the use of hymns, Psalms and spiritual songs. Doubt the promotion of the twin

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activities of worship and reflection should be a major pillar of personal counseling, so much of the discomfort of believers may be relieved by worship and gratitude for all that God is and all that he has done. This is the way to lift up the soul and to trample down discouragement and difficulty.

Thanksgiving, coupled with intelligent reflection on the ways and promises of God in the word, and his past blessings to us, more than anything else dispels sadness, anxiety and insecurity. Certainly it dispels vindictiveness, selfishness and worldliness. This is why worship should not be worldly in character, borrowing the polluted styles of worldly entertainment. True worship is antidote to all this, lifting the soul far above the self-centered, sin-centered thinking and emotionalism of a fallen world. Is a believer angry with someone who has offended him? The answer is to engage in worship and praise to God for all his amazing kindness and the unworthy anger is shamed away, self-pity withers and dies before a glorious savior, therefore each one of us is urged to reflect praise, thanksgiving and adoration.

For Knowledge and Happiness:

One of the greatest aims of inter-personal ministry should be the promotion and encouragement of individual Bible study, so that all may be filled with all knowledge (Romans 15:14).

Therefore counselors should urge counselee to be great learners to read the Word of God, together with commentary which can assist them with difficult verses.

Treatment of the importance of sacrifice and service, the fifth pillar is generally absent from counseling books, yet they are essential to the spiritual wellbeing of believer, for this is what we were saved for. In Romans 15:16 Paul makes a seemingly mysterious statement, and speaks in an almost priestly manner, saying that God made him - "the minister of Jesus Christ to the Gentiles, ministering the gospel of God, that the offering up of the Gentiles might be acceptable". He seems to say, "In evangelizing Gentiles I am offering them up as a priest does, making an offering in the temple". Paul tells us what he means in chapter 12 'I beseech you therefore, brethren, by the mercies of God, that you present your bodies a living sacrifice, holy, acceptable unto God, which is your reasonable service. Gentiles are being won for the Lord to sacrifice themselves to his service to live and witness for him and be entirely at his disposal. This is the greatest of all personal ministry, the urging of each other to be wholly offered up and given up to

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the Lord's service. If Christ comes first, then all other things fall into place, which is partly what the savior meant when he said: Therefore take no thought, saying what shall we eat? Or what shall we drink? Or, where withal shall we be clothed? But seek ye first the kingdom of God and all these things shall be added unto you (Mathew 6:31-33).

Outgoing Caring Lifestyle advanced: pillar of personal ministry that we should press and urge one another to be an outgoing and caring people is seen strongly in the words of Romans 15: 1-3. "We then that are strong ought to bear the infirmities of the weak and not to please ourselves. Let everyone of us please his neighbor for his good to edification, for even Christ pleased not himself, but as it is written, the reproaches of them that reproached thee fell on me".

FRIENDSHIP AND CHEER: concluding pillar of inter-personal ministry is as fundamental and essential as the others the duty of imparting friendship and cheer. As we are looking at Romans 15, we will find this in the penultimate verse - verse 32, "That I may come unto you with joy by the will of God and man with you be refreshed". It will be so good to be with you, Paul says, for it will cheer my heart no end, and refresh my spirit to have the fellowship of you dear friends we must be keen to urge one another to provide friendship and cheer, it is our duty, as well as a most uplifting activity. We say to husbands and wives at wedding services, you have a duty to cheer each other up. And we all have this duty whether friends or fellow laborers, we have a duty to encourage and uplift those around us, and not to inflict upon them our heavy moods and despondent thoughts, let alone our complaints and miseries. What importance is the Christian counseling to Christian Education?

History of Christian Counselling

Since 1986, the Christian counselling & educational foundation (CCEF) has set the pace in biblical counselling.

CCEF teaches people how to explore the wisdom and depth of the bible and apply its grace - centred message to the problems of daily living. It continues to strive to fulfil its mission to restore Christ to the church and persons through counselling services, classroom training, distance education, internships, publications and conferences.

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As a general rule, both Christian counselling and secular counselling share the same desire to help people overcome their problems, find meaning and joy in life, and become healthy and well-adjusted individuals, both mentally and emotionally.

The word “counselling” can have multiple meanings, including offering advice and encouragement, sharing wisdom, and skills, setting goals, resolving conflicts etc.

Counsellors always probe the past so as to confirm whether the problem happened a week ago or during childhood in an attempt to repair the present. Sometimes, they explore the possible effects of physical and chemical imbalances that can cause physiological problems.

A major part of counselling is resolving and restoring conflicts between peoples.

Foundationally, Christian counselling is distinct from secular counselling. Christian counselling rises to another dimension. “In contrast to psychologically integrated system, biblical counselling seeks to carefully discover those areas in which a Christian may be disobedient to the principles and commands of scriptures and to help him learn how to lovingly submit to God’s will”, Christian counsellors are able to do that because they have an absolute standard by which to measure their objectives and evaluate their counsellor’s life style. They see the bible as the source of all truth. 2Timothy 3:16 - 17 says: “All scriptures is God’s -breathed and is useful for teaching, rebuking, correcting and training in righteousness, so that the man of god may be thoroughly equipped for every good work”, The secular counsellor has no such standard, but instead, they use the latest psychological findings or societal norm, both of which change with the wind of time. Therefore, a secular counsellor has no absolutes with which to judge morals and the choices people make. Christian counsellors understand that the bible has a lot of practical wisdom about human nature, marriage and family, human suffering, and so much more. By using biblical concepts in counselling, they can instruct people in the way they should go and also hold them accountable. Psalm 119: 24 says: “your statutes are my delight, they are my counsellor”. Although Christian counsellors often use skills from the field of secular psychology and counselling, they recognized that the bible, not psychology, is the final authority. “His divine power has given us everything we need for life and godliness through our knowledge of Him who called us by His own glory and goodness”. (2Peter 1:3) A Christian counsellor’s major strategy is to help their clients substitute biblical truth for errors they go about their day-to-day lives. They know that the truth when known,

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delivered and obeyed, sets people free. When people are set free, they are fulfilling their true calling “then you shall know the truth, and the truth will set you free” (John 8:32).

Biblical counselling aims for heart change, not merely behaviour change. Christians have been counselling one another from scripture since the early church of the 1st century CE. The modern technical term for using the bible as the basis for Christian counselling is “nouthetic counselling”. The institution for nouthetic studies explains “nouthetic counselling as consisting of lovingly confronting people out of deep concern in order to help them make those changes that God requires”. Bible based or nouthetic counsellors operate from a set of common presuppositions regarding the bedrock foundation of the authority of the bible as the inspired and infallible word of God, sufficient to meet every need. 2Timothy 3:16 relates, “All scripture is inspired by god and profitable for teaching, for reproof, for correction, for learning in righteousness, so that the man of God may be adequate, equipped for every good work”. Therefore, the nouthetic counsellor relies not on his own ideas but, “gives counsel from the scriptures that directs believers to not only see things that need changing in their lives but also how they are to change, according to compassionate counsellors.

Significance of the Study

Counseling is the foundation (Bed Rock) of Christianity and success is a basic component of any Christianity that acknowledges and applies this fact. Despite this, counseling in Christianity has not been so effective. Increasing numbers of Christians have facilitated the usage of Christian counseling.

The present research is therefore considered significant as it aims at drawing the attention of Christians and the world at large to the potency of this indispensable tool (counseling) made available for Christian success and maturity.

In particular, the findings of this study will benefit the field of full-time pastors and some part-time pastors who have been achieving little or nothing in their counseling ministry due to improper education on what it takes to counsel for effective results.

Teachers, armed with the findings of this study, will be in a position to remedy problems of non-existence of counseling or poor knowledge gained from untrained counselors in their world.

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Specifically, as a result of the findings of this study, Christian counselors will have a deeper understanding of language condition as it relates to the counselors character and success in Christian counseling. This is particularly applicable to the need for the best attention and problems and their settings which are always experienced at the beginning of any counseling process. Also the present research has the potential to influence reading counseling instructional material practices in schools, churches, libraries and other resource centers both in Plateau State, Nigeria and even in South Africa. Furthermore, this research holds the potential to guide curriculum development and developers as well as other resource centers as a reference material, since undergraduates from universities are advised to go to resource centers for such materials to help them learn better.

How are the regarded as bed rock of Christianity?

Skills in Counseling

Unlike more casual discussions between friends, the helping relationship is characterized by a clear purpose. That of helping the counselee, the helper's needs are mostly met elsewhere and they should not depend on the counselee for love, affirmation or help. In the helping relationship, counselors lay aside their own struggles or conflicts, seeks to become aware of counselee needs, and communicate both understanding and a willingness to help. The help giving process may be complicated and it is impossible to summarize in a few paragraphs. Every counseling situation is unique but all effective counselors use a variety of skills, the most basic of which include the following:

1. **Attending Skills:** Counselors must try to give undivided attention to each counselee, even though this can be difficult to sustain. Attending is done through
 - (a) Eye contact - looking without staring as a way to convey concern and understanding.
 - (b) Posture, which should be relaxed rather than tense. (Nobody feels comfortable with an up-tight counselor).
 - (c) Gestures, including head nods that are natural but not excessive or distracting. The counselor communicates attention when he or she courteous, kind and strongly motivated to understand. Recognize that your own fatigue, impatience, preoccupations with other matters, day dreaming or restlessness can all prevent you from giving careful attention to the counselee. I would emphasize again

that people (counselors) helping is demanding work that involves sensitivity, genuine expressions of care, and alertness to what the counselee may be trying to communicate.

2. **Listening Skills:** This involves more than passive or halfhearted attention to the words that come from another person. Effective listening is an active process involves: - Being able to set aside your own conflicts, biases and preoccupations so you can concentrate on what the counselee is communicating.
- (a) Avoiding subtle verbal and nonverbal expressions of disapproval or judgment about what is being said, even when the content is offensive or shocking.
 - (b) Using both your eyes and your ears to detect messages that come from the tone of voice, pace of talking, ideas, that are repeated, posture, gestures, facial expressions and other clues apart from what the person is saying.
 - (c) Hearing not what the counselee says, but noticing
What gets left out? Noticing the counselee's physical characteristics and general appearance such as grooming and dress.
 - (d) Waiting patiently through periods of silence or tears as the counselee summons enough courage to share something painful or pauses to collect his or her thoughts.
 - (e) Looking at the counselee as he or she speaks, but without either staring or letting our eyes wander around the room. That you can accept the counselee, even though you may not condone his or her actions, values, or beliefs. Sometimes, it can be helpful to imagine yourself in the counselee's situation and attempt to see things from his or her point of view.
- Responding Skills:** - There was a time when counselors were taught to pay attention and listen, but to make only occasional specific comments. These comments were intended to spur the counselee on to more evaluation until he or she came up with

solutions to the problem. That approach left people frustrated because the counselor appeared to be listening and not doing much more. But in addition to their listening, good counselors are good respondents. Jesus is an example, He listened carefully to the perplexed men and they walked along the road to Emmaus, but his helping also was marked by action and specific verbal responses. How do we respond in helpful ways?

- (a) **Leading** is a skill that lets the counselor gently direct the conversation. **“What happened next?” “Tell me what you mean by --?” “Then what?”** are brief questions that can steer the discussion in directions that will give useful information. Occasionally, you also will need to remind the counselees that they are off track and gently suggest that they come back to the thing you were telling me before.
 - (b) **Reflecting** is way of letting counselees know that we are with them and able to understand how they feel or think. Examples, include statements like, **“you must feel”, “I bet that was frustrating”, that must have been fun”,** all of these reflects what is going in counseling. **Be careful not to reflect after every statement but instead, do it periodically.**
 - (c) **Summarizing** what has been going on also can be away of reflecting and stimulating more counselee exploration. It also lets you check the accuracy of what you have been hearing.
3. **Questioning Skills:** If done carefully this can bring forth a great deal of useful information. The best questions are those that require at least a few sentence to answer (e.g.: **“Tell me about your marriage” “What sort of things are making you unhappy?”**) rather than those that can be answered in one word. (**“Are you married?”, Are you unhappy?” “What is your age?”**) It is easier to feel uncomfortable when we are stuck and sure what to say next. It is best to avoid questions that begin with **why**, because they tend to sound judgmental or they stimulate long intellectual discussions and analyses that keep the counselee from coming to grips with real feelings or hurts. Even when counselees want to be honest and cooperative, there are issues or piece information they never think to
4. mention. Prompting and probing are special forms of questioning that help people talk in more details about themselves. These prompts and probes may not always sound like questions, sometimes they are more like interjections. Examples are:

“Tell me more about that?” “What happened then?” “This means that ----?” “So -
---?” “Then ----?”

What do you mean by the things that----?” often, these give you pertinent information, but they also help counselees better clarify the issues they are presenting.

5. **Challenging Skills:** Sometimes, it is not enough for a counselor to show empathy, to express understanding, or to give encouragement. Counselees need to be challenged to face problems they would rather avoid, develop new perspectives about themselves or their environment, and take action to resolve conflict with others, or stop bitterness, whining or other self-defeating behaviors and attitudes. Every counselor meets with people who enjoy complaining, and feeling like victims but who are reluctant to take any action to change. Despite their complaints many of these people are afraid to change, don't know how to change, perhaps have something biochemical that is preventing the change, or in some cases feel more comfortable staying with their problems rather than taking responsibility and the risk to do something different. For many years, counselors talked about confronting people to get moving and do something about their situations. Confrontation, however, is a biting word that implies condemnation and criticism. Some Christians work on the assumption that counseling and confrontation are synonymous terms. For them to counsel is to confront, this has neither Biblical nor psychological support. Sometime, Jesus confronted people, but more often he used a gentle approach. In contrast to the more negative and condemnatory concept of condemnation, challenge is a more positive term that implies respect and a prod for the counselee to do whatever it takes to change. Counselee can be challenged to face and do something about sin in their lives, failure, inconsistencies, excuses, harmful attitudes, or other self-defeating behavior and ways of thinking. At times, counselees need to be challenged to admit that they are behaving in ways that are irresponsible, harmful to others or making things worse rather than better. Sometimes people need to be challenged about their perception of themselves or others. For example, parents might perceive their teenage son as being rebellious and intent on making life miserable for them. This may not at all be an accurate portrayal of the son or of the struggles that might be going on inside of him. Whatever the situation, challenging is most effective when it is done in a loving, gentle, nonjudgmental but firm manner. If

there are several issues, about which you can challenge your counselee, don't raise them all at once, since this can overwhelm the person, focus should be on one issue at a time. As counselors might expect, people respond differently to being challenged, sometimes, there is agreement with the counselor, a determination to make changes or a confession of sin with a significant experience of forgiveness. Often challenges bring resistance, guilt, hurt, or anger, it is important to let counsees respond verbally to your challenge. Give them time to discuss alternative ways of behaving and then guide them as they make changes.

4. **Teaching Skills:** In many ways, all counseling techniques are specialized forms of spiritual and psychological education. The counselor is an educator who uses different ways to teach: instruction, modeling, telling brief stories, pointing to movies or video recordings that can be helpful and guiding counsees as they learn by experience to deal with problems of life.

Like other less personal forms of education, counseling is more effective when the counselee's different senses are involved, it helps, too, when discussions are specific rather than vague, and focused on concrete situations ("How can I control my temper when I am criticized by my wife?") rather than on nebulous goals ("I want life to be happier").

One powerful learning tool is the immediacy response. This involves the ability of a counselor and counselee to discuss openly and directly what is happening in the "immediate", here and now of the relationship. "I think our conversation has stalled", a counselor might say, for example, or "I feel that you are resisting everything that I say", such honest, on-the-spot statements let individuals express and deal with feelings and other issues before they grow and then break down the counseling process. Immediacy responses help both counselors and counsees to better understand how the counselee's actions or attitudes affect or may be seen by others. This understanding is an important educational aspect of counseling. Usually, immediacy responses are initiated by the counselor but not always. At times, counsees learn to use immediacy responses to challenge their counselors. This, too, gives opportunity to discuss what is happening within the counseling relationship that may have a bearing on the counseling process and issues. These responses from counsees can also challenge counselors to consider how they are doing (or failing to do) their work. If the counselor is failing; consider this

primarily as an issue that is considered by the counselor outside the counseling room and with the counselee.

Informing: Is not the same as advice-giving that we raised caution about earlier. Advice - givers often lack enough accurate knowledge of a situation to give competent advice. Their advice -giving can encourage counsees to be dependent but if the advice proves to be invalid, it is the counselor who later is blamed and made to feel responsible for giving bad direction. Whenever you are asked for advice or inclined to give advice, be sure that you are well informed about the situation. Ask yourself, do I have enough information and expertise to give this person competent advice? What might be the end results of this advice-giving? Is it likely to make the counselee more dependent? Does the person know how to act upon the advice? Can I handle the reactions that might come if the advice is rejected or proved wrong? If you do give advice, offer it in the form of tentative suggestion, then give the counselee time to react or talk through your advice and follow up to see the extent to which the advice was helpful and is being followed.

5. **Filtering Skills:** Counselors are not innately skeptical people who disbelieve everything a counselee says, but it is wise to remember that counselee's don't always tell the whole story and don't always say what they really want, need, intend. Sometimes a counselee deliberately presents a distorted picture, leaving out embarrassing or potentially incriminating details.

Often counsees fail to see their problems in broader perspective and sometimes they come for help with one problem but fail to see or are reluctant to raise other deeper problems. As you counsel, therefore, mentally try to sort through the counselee's word. What is she or he really asking? What does this person really want from a counselor? Does it seem as though there may problems or issues other than the ones that are being presented? At times people talk about one issue, but they really have little desire to change. Instead, they are looking for sympathy, attention, catharsis, another person's view point, a way to escape from some unpleasant situation, or words from you that they can use as ammunition to attack somebody they strongly dislike. As you listen, you begin to suspect these underlying motives and you realize that often these aren't even recognized by the counselee. In time, you will want to raise these and talk about them in counseling. The counselor does not try to invent new issues or force counsees to consider topics, they don't want to discuss. Even so, your work will be more effective if

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you learn to listen with sensitivity and try not to accept everything at face value. It helps as well, if you are aware that no person, not even counselors, can listen with complete objectivity. We all have personal, family, cultural, theological and other filters that help us sort out and make sense of the information that comes into our mind. These filters help make sense of the world, but they also can add bias to the ways counselors listen. All of these point again to the counselor's need for wisdom and discernment. Some of this comes with experience, but Christians know that sensitivity more often comes when we pray, asking for the insight, guidance, clarity and accurate perception that comes from the Holy Spirit.

Conclusion

The spiritual state of the average believer or Christian sets the tempo of the counseling relationship. In a situation where a great number of Christians are stalked and assailed by a myriad of challenges in life viz: economic, occupational, cultural, traditional, demonic, fears and other numerous concerns, the need for counselors naturally arises. These excruciating pains and challenges exert immense intensity of pressure which definitely seeks for a way of alleviating the stress. God has before time made available multidimensional counseling as a resource through which he extends his helping arm to his suffering and ailing family. Through this, he passes via willing and consecrated channels (counselors) to teach, encourage, educate, revive, discipline, recuperate and mould his children depending on their need.

In a null shell therefore, counseling in all its multi-faceted dimension scope and approaches aids the willing counselee to resolve crisis and find a firm footing in life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this work, I wish to recommend the following:

- (a) Churches and ministerial training schools, bible colleges, seminaries, universities and colleges should invest more on counseling curriculum that is loaded to include diverse dimensions of counseling. The essence of this is to expose pastors and would-be counselors to diverse areas so that they can be practically useful to the flock.

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- (b) Church bodies and training schools should go beyond pastoral psychology but rather initiate would be pastors and counselors into core spirituality, real and functional relationship with God and dept Christology.
- (c) Pastoral counselors should be trained to make referrals both within and across their denominations to enhance professionalism and pursue client satisfaction.
- (d) Church or church organizations should employ well - trained Christian counselors alongside pastoral staff so as to meet the specific unspoken needs of counselees which professional pastors may not be able to meet because of lack of time and proper exposure to counseling requirements.
- (e) The counseling environment should be designed in such a way that it is stimulating, elicits warmth, comfort, privacy and generally commercial for the counselee to be expressive and relax.